

QUIZ**LAST NAME: EJIMBA****FIRST NAME: BENIGNA****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used MSWord 2019 on Mac

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. One of the following will not amount to plagiarism:

- Quoting someone else's work without acknowledging the source.
- Paraphrasing a publication on the internet and free for all without acknowledging the source.
- Quoting from another person's work, an information of general knowledge without acknowledging the source.¹**
- Asking another person's help to write a paper and submitting it as one's own idea without acknowledging the help received.

2. In paraphrasing an information from another person's work, it is not necessary for:

¹ EUCLID, *ACA-401 Coursepack* (Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2015) 10, 30, accessed January 5, 2020, <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>.

- The information to be enclosed in quotation marks and the source cited.²**
 - The words and style used to be different from that of the original author.
 - The information provided to be an accurate representation of what the original author wrote.
 - The source of the information to be indicated.
3. **According to Turabian, one should evaluate and reconsider a proposed research question if the answer:**
- Is not easily known and there is good evidence to support the answer.
 - Is easily known and there is evidence to support the answer.³**
 - Can be possibly disproved by a compelling evidence.
 - Is not easily known and can be possibly disproved.
4. **In the final draft of the introduction of a research paper, one must not include:**
- A statement of the research question and its significance.
 - A brief statement of the findings of the research.⁴**
 - A brief background of prior research.
 - The hypothesis or claim of the research.

² EUCLID, *ACA-401 Coursepack* (Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2015) 24, accessed January 5, 2020, <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, rev. Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013) 20.

⁴ *Ibid.*, 70-71.

5. **A bibliography should ordinarily contain all sources cited in the text of the research paper and labeled adequately. However, there are certain exceptions and one of the following is not an exception:**
- A bibliography may include all sources cited in text as well as those consulted but not cited.
 - A bibliography may not include all sources cited and labelled selected bibliography with a headnote that explains the principle of the selection.
 - A bibliography may list the works of a single author, therefore omitting the name of the author without any description.⁵**
 - A bibliography may be annotated with a brief description of the content relevant to the research and labelled annotated bibliography.
6. **For citations in a bibliography one of the following does not accurately represent information that must be present:**
- Author(s), editor(s), title, publisher, year of publication, edition and volume number.
 - Editors, title, year of publication, and a URL for online source.
 - Author(s), year of publication, publisher, volume, page and edition number.⁶**
 - Translator(s), year of publication, title, publishers and place of publication.
7. **According to Bloomberg and Volpe, one of the following does not accurately represent what an abstract should contain:**

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, rev. Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013) 93.

⁶ *Ibid.*, 107.

- Title of the study, the research problem, the hypothesis, the literature review, research findings and limitations of the research.**⁷
- Title of the study, key findings and conclusions, the data sources that informed the study, and theories that guided the study.
- Title of the study, the research tradition, key findings, conclusions and recommendations.
- Qualitative research tradition, methods and procedure used for the collection and analysis of data.

8. **One of the following is not true of a good literature review:**

- It should provide a clear picture of current concepts, theories and data relevant to your topic.
- In a research paper, literature review should be done only within the introduction and literature review chapters.**⁸
- It should give the readers a summary of existing knowledge of the topic and show the writer's ability to interpret ideas and integrate data with it.
- It helps the writer to have a full understanding of the topic and also avoid duplication of research.

9. **Which of the following shows a wrong use of foreign words in English text?**

- The study material discussed *inter alia* the use of punctuations and quotations.

⁷ Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2008) 168.

⁸ *Ibid.*, 48.

- Service to humanity is our *raison d'être*.
- The parliament set up *ad hoc* committees to tackle the health crisis.⁹**
- The Jakišnica, Dudići and Dražica are situated in the northwestern part of Pag Island.

10. **According to the European Commission, one of the following is not a good use of numbers in English text:**

- Of all the delegates, 13 were in favor of the motion, while 7 were against it.
- About three hundred lives were lost during the insurgency.
- The government has budgeted \$3 700 000bn for the prevention of the virus.¹⁰**
- The study material in chapter one discussed the theoretical basis of research writing, while chapter 13 gave practical examples of a research paper.

⁹ European Commission Directorate-General for Translation, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. 7th ed. 2011, 31, accessed January 26, 2020 http://ec.europa.eu/translation/english/guidelines/documents/styleguide_english_dgt_en.pdf.

¹⁰ Ibid., 23-24

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